

One-Step Blade Coating of Inverted Double-Cation Perovskite Solar Cells from a Green Precursor Solvent

Johannes Küffner^{a}, Jonas Hanisch^a, Tina Wahl^a, Julia Zillner^a, Erik Ahlswede^{a*}, Michael Powalla^a*

^aCenter for Solar Energy and Hydrogen Research Baden-Württemberg (ZSW), Meitnerstrasse 1, Stuttgart, 70563, Germany.

*Corresponding Authors: johannes.kueffner@zsw-bw.de, erik.ahlswede@zsw-bw.de

KEYWORDS

Perovskite solar cell, green solvent, scalable, blade coating, one-step, double-cation, low-temperature

ABSTRACT

Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have recently gained power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) of up to 25.5% on lab-scale nearly exclusively processed from precursor solutions involving harmful and polluting solvents like dimethylformamide (DMF). However, solution processing of green and environmentally safe solvents such as dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) via scalable printing is

challenging mainly caused by two reasons: firstly pronounced precursor solution dewetting on the subjacent layer and secondly its complex quenching process. In this work, we report on one-step blade coating of inverted (p-i-n) double-cation PSCs using solely DMSO at low processing temperatures. To avoid dewetting of the DMSO-based solution on the hydrophobic hole transport layer (HTL) and to realize adequate quenching, a blade coated wetting agent of silicon oxide nanoparticles at the HTL/perovskite interface and gas stream-assisted drying is applied, respectively. Trends in absorber grain size, morphology, crystallinity and elemental composition of samples from both toxic and green solvent concepts are compared revealing analogous findings. Consequently, PSCs blade coated from DMSO achieve PCEs of up to 16.7% on a 0.24 cm² active area comparable to the ones from a DMF:DMSO mixture (16.9%) and thus demonstrating that using toxic DMF is unnecessary. This represents an important step for bringing PSCs solution processed from environmentally friendly precursor solvents closer to industrial implementation.

INTRODUCTION

In only one decade, hybrid organic-inorganic metal-halide perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have achieved an impressive rise in power conversion efficiency (PCE) from 3.8%¹ to a tremendous level of 25.5%.² Perovskite thin films can inexpensively be processed at low temperatures³⁻⁵ and from solution by scalable printing techniques⁶⁻⁸ such as spray,^{9,10} blade¹¹⁻¹³ or D-bar,¹⁴⁻¹⁷ and slot-die coating,¹⁸⁻²¹ or inkjet printing.²²⁻²⁴ Here, we investigate blade coating because of its easy handling, low ink usage and readily transferability to high-throughput industrial scale roll-to-roll (R2R) slot-die coating.²⁵⁻²⁷

Methylammonium lead triiodide (MAPbI₃) is the most widely used lead-halide perovskite material for PSCs as it is a defect tolerant semiconductor with extraordinary optoelectronic properties.²⁸ However, in recent years, MAPbI₃ perovskite absorber have been replaced by multi-cation

perovskite precursor mixtures such as triple-cation formamidinium (FA)/methyl ammonium (MA)/cesium (Cs)-based perovskite compositions because of their higher resulting device efficiency and intrinsic structural stability.^{29–31} By now, the research focus lies more on double-cation perovskite materials especially due to their thermal stability, which normally contain FA and/or Cs avoiding the highly volatile MA.^{31,32}

Unfortunately, producing a uniform and high-quality perovskite thin film from such more complex precursor solutions on large area via a scalable printing technique, such as blade coating, might be additionally challenging due to their intricate solution chemistry.^{33,34} Thereby, next to the more technological vacuum-assisted perovskite conversion,^{35–38} the quenching methods via heat and a gas stream are considered to be easily scalable.^{33,34} The latter is the most promising because it can enable room temperature (RT) processing, which at the same time decouples the solution coating and the drying inducing the nucleation before crystallization. Consequently, this might ensure high process controllability and reproducibility.^{33,34}

Multi-cation perovskite precursor solutions usually utilize solvent mixtures of toxic *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) as main component and only little amount of co-solvents^{29,30,39} also in order to guarantee solubility of all precursor materials including cesium iodide (CsI).^{40,41} However, for upscaling to mass production and commercialization, appropriate handling of the toxic main constituent of the solvent system must be already considered during the initial development phase^{42,43} which is the focus of this work.

For the case of MAPbI₃-based perovskite, several studies have utilized solvents and solvent mixtures that reduce or eliminate the use or generation of substances hazardous to humans, animals, plants, and the environment⁴⁴, also referred to as green solvents,⁴⁵ aiming to demonstrate alternatives to DMF.^{46–53} However regarding multi-cation perovskite thin films, reports

particularly concerning blade coating describe, to the best of our knowledge, merely the utilization of toxic solvent systems.^{4,11,54-59} More nonconventional solvents and co-solvents used for upscaling PSCs are acetonitrile (ACN),^{5,20,25,26} 2-methoxyethanol (2-ME)^{5,14,18,60-62} or 2-methylpyrazine (2-MP)⁶³ but it is up for debate if these solvents are sufficiently green.⁵³

A fully green and sustainable solvent such as pure dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) would be much more preferable to use for PSC fabrication^{64,65} as recently presented in a comprehensive health and environmental impact analysis including a life cycle assessment (LCA) by Vidal et al.⁶⁶ Despite the general disadvantage of carrying toxins or dissolved materials with it across the skin membranes, the study shows that DMSO offers the lowermost human health and environmental impact compared to all other typical polar aprotic solvents for producing the perovskite layer of PSCs,^{66,67} which normally exhibit a strong electronegative polar group in the solvent molecule. Moreover, DMSO has a high donor number (D_N) (Table S1), which was proposed as figure of merit to describe the coordination ability of the solvent with perovskite precursors especially to lead ions (Pb^{2+}). This leads to an excellent solubility of the perovskite precursors in DMSO.^{5,68} However, utilizing pure DMSO implies two main challenges in contrast to DMF or mixtures of DMF and DMSO: (i) increased dewetting on the subjacent layer,^{48,69} especially on poly(triaryl amine) (PTAA), due to the high DMSO surface tension of 42.8 mN m^{-170} and a high viscosity of 2.0 cP^5 causing inhomogeneous perovskite films on large area^{3,5,71,72} and a reduced processing speed;^{5,66} (ii) complex quenching and longer solvent evaporation periods of the wet film^{73,74} when using low processing temperatures due to its low vapor pressure (VP) and higher boiling point (BP) of $189 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ compared to the one of DMF ($153 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)⁶⁶ as summarized in Table S1. Since PSCs with perovskite layers fabricated from pure DMSO have normally exhibited poor device performance^{46,48,69,72} due to the mentioned challenges, this solvent system has been rarely

used except of very few reports. They refer to the fabrication of lead iodide (PbI₂) films in a two-step method⁷⁵ or, when utilizing a one-step method, to the deposition of single-cation perovskite layers via a meniscus coating technique^{46,72} and spin coating.^{48,76–78}

Even fewer studies are reported on double- or multi-cation perovskite produced by solely DMSO solution processing. Meniscus coating of a pure DMSO double-cation precursor solution has been reported by He et al. but the perovskite composition still contained MA.¹⁵ In contrast, Galagan et al. investigated slot-die coating of MA-free double-cation perovskite films in merely DMSO which was unfortunately only feasible by adding the hazardous co-solvent 2-butoxyethanol (2-BE).⁶⁹ Furthermore, Zhang et al. recently described a double-cation perovskite solution deposited from pure DMSO, however only for hardly scalable spin coating and antisolvent-assisted conversion.⁷⁹

For the first time, we here demonstrate blade coating of MA-free double-cation perovskite in a one-step process for inverted (p-i-n) PSCs from solely green DMSO without co-solvents or additives at low processing temperatures, which is an important step toward environmentally friendly industry-relevant solution processing of PSCs. The nonpolar polymer PTAA is utilized as hole transport layer (HTL) because of its efficient carrier transport properties.⁸⁰ To prevent dewetting of the precursor solution on PTAA, a blade coated silicon oxide (SiO₂) nanoparticle (NP) wetting agent at the HTL/perovskite interface is applied which enhances the PTAA surface energy.^{80,81} Consequently, there is no need of the widely utilized addition of amphiphilic surfactants to the perovskite precursor solution, such as L- α -phosphatidylcholine (LP), to lower its surface tension.^{5,11,27,55,60,82–84} The surfactant might alter the perovskite crystallization and adsorb predominantly at the perovskite surface hindering an unproblematic continuation of the device stack by solution processing.^{80,85,86} Furthermore, sufficient quenching is realized by gas stream-assisted drying⁸⁰ as similarly reported in literature.^{3,5,16,17,56,60,61,87,88}

Moreover, we compare trends in perovskite grain size, morphology, crystallinity and elemental composition of samples fabricated from both toxic and green solvent concepts. Thus, PSCs with 0.24 cm² active area blade coated from merely DMSO achieve almost equal device performance of up to 16.7% PCE compared to the ones from a toxic DMF:DMSO mixture (16.9%) disclosing the capability of our approach to prevent the use of toxic DMF.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this work, we fabricate PSCs in the inverted planar device stack on glass consisting of indium tin oxide (ITO)/PTAA/SiO₂ NPs/FA_{0.83}CS_{0.17}Pb(I_{0.87}Br_{0.13})₃ (FACsPbIBr)/[6,6]-phenyl-C₆₁-butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM)/bathocuproine (BCP)/silver (Ag) (Figure 1a). The chosen chemical composition of the double-cation perovskite allows stable absorber layers avoiding MA with a bandgap of >1.60 eV that might be as well suitable for tandem applications.^{32,89} Figure 1b presents a cross-section scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of a typical solar cell device in this study.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic illustration of the inverted device architecture with SiO₂ NPs located at the PTAA/perovskite interface. (b) SEM cross-section image of a PSC (ITO/PTAA/SiO₂ NPs/FACsPbIBr/PCBM/BCP/Ag) with a perovskite layer fabricated from solely DMSO.

The perovskite precursors are either dissolved in a toxic 4:1 (vol:vol) DMF:DMSO mixture or in merely green DMSO. To prevent dewetting of the precursor solution on the hydrophobic PTAA, a blade coated SiO₂ NP wetting agent is applied at the HTL/perovskite interface which bases upon our previous work.^{80,81} Figure S1 clearly indicates that without the use of the NP wetting agent on top of PTAA the perovskite precursor solution in pure DMSO is non-wetting on PTAA and did not remain on the substrate after blade coating, while in the case of PTAA/NPs fully covered and homogeneous double-cation perovskite layers are obtained after annealing.

For deposition of the perovskite film, we use nitrogen (N₂) gas stream-assisted blade coating⁸⁰ in a N₂-filled glovebox with a plate temperature of 40 °C, which we consider as low-temperature processing. Figure 2 displays a schematic illustration of blade coating and the drying process.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of N₂ gas stream-assisted blade coating utilized in this study.

We emphasize that engineering of process parameters, such as flow rate, direction of the gas stream and delay time after wet film deposition until quenching as well as blade coating and gas knife

moving speed, is critical and led to different ideal process conditions for both separately optimized recipes of each solvent system. For instance, earlier tests revealed that more uniform perovskite films are obtained when choosing larger gas stream flow rates. They result in higher degree of supersaturation and therefore leading to a boosted nucleation density with compact perovskite domains.^{56,90} Details on the procedure are given in the Experimental Section.

Evaluation of Perovskite Morphology and Crystal Grains. To evaluate the morphology and crystal grains of the resulting perovskite from a toxic and green solvent system, we compare SEM top-view images of perovskite layers blade coated on ITO/PTAA/SiO₂ NPs from a 4:1 (vol:vol) DMF:DMSO mixture and pure DMSO (Figure 3). Both films are annealed at temperatures of either 100 °C or 150 °C for 10 min as illustrated in Figure 3a-d. Figure 3e illustrates corresponding histograms of crystal grain size distribution determined from SEM images with lower magnification and a larger image section (not shown) than in Figure 3a-d, respectively, to increase statistics.

Figure 3. SEM top-view images of double-cation perovskite layers blade coated on ITO/PTAA/SiO₂ NPs from a precursor solution in different solvent systems, namely 4:1 (vol:vol)

DMF:DMSO mixture (a, c) and DMSO (b, d), both annealed at temperatures of 100 °C (a, b) or 150 °C (c, d). (e) Corresponding histograms of crystal grain size distribution determined from SEM images with lower magnification (not shown) than in panel a-d.

The morphology of the perovskite layer fabricated from DMSO does not significantly differ from the one of the DMF:DMSO mixture for each annealing temperature. When identifying the crystal grain size, the samples show an absolute increase in mean crystal grain size of circa 90 nm (DMF:DMSO) and 110 nm (DMSO), when the annealing temperature is altered from 100 °C to 150 °C, which corresponds to a relative increase of over 55% and 75%, respectively, as illustrated in Figure 3c, d and e. Thus, the increase in growth is nearly similar in both cases. Figure 3e discloses a slightly smaller mean crystal grain size of approximately 140 nm of the perovskite layer fabricated by utilizing DMSO compared to DMF:DMSO (160 nm), when choosing an annealing temperature of 100 °C. The reason for that might be the different BPs of 153 °C and 189 °C of DMF and DMSO (Table S1), respectively.

In the case of an annealing temperature of 150 °C, the mean grain sizes of circa 250 nm of samples deposited from both solvent systems are similar (Figure 3e) because an annealing temperature of 150 °C is high enough to fully evaporate pure DMSO analogically to a DMF:DMSO mixture. The grain size is larger for the higher annealing temperature of 150 °C due to enhanced grain coarsening as reported in literature.⁹¹⁻⁹³

Figure S2 presents top-view SEM images of the same samples with a lower magnification. The images indicate a homogeneous layer with full coverage in the case of the toxic DMF:DMSO solvent system as well as of the green pure DMSO solvent with both annealing temperatures.

To investigate the surface roughness of the FACsPbIBr layers, we measured SEM cross-sections of complete solar cell device stacks with perovskite active layer blade coated from a precursor

solution in the two solvent systems (Figure S3). We observe similar surface roughness independently from the solvent system and the annealing temperature. The electron transport layer (ETL) of PCBM completely covers the perovskite layer. We observe larger grains preferentially in the case of the higher annealing temperature (Figure S3c, d) as already presented in Figure 3c, d. Furthermore, a homogeneous coverage and no voids are found at the HTL/perovskite interface.^{19,60,80} From Figure S3, no clear statement can be made on the absorber thicknesses in relation to the four parameter sets, since perovskite layers exhibit slight thickness variations over the $3 \times 6 \text{ cm}^2$ substrate caused by the characteristic of the blade coating process itself.

From the SEM studies, we conclude that the perovskite morphology is homogeneous and the mean grain size, grain size distribution and surface roughness of samples from toxic and green solvent systems are comparable. This fact is mainly attributed to the sufficient quenching by gas stream-assisted drying and to the improved wetting properties of both perovskite precursor solutions on the nonwetting PTAA layer, especially the one with solely DMSO, with the aid of the NP wetting agent.^{80,81}

Investigation of Perovskite Crystallographic and Optical Properties. X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements are conducted on annealed perovskite layers to investigate their crystal structure fabricated from the toxic DMF:DMSO and the green DMSO solvent systems with both annealing temperatures (Figure S4).

XRD patterns disclose the formation of the perovskite structure independent of the solvent system and annealing temperature. All peaks from the films can be indexed to the perovskite phase or the subjacent ITO. Hence, that means that the films indicate a pure perovskite phase without formamidinium iodide (FAI), CsI or yellow phases of formamidinium lead iodide (FAPbI₃) or

cesium lead iodide (CsPbI_3) and PbI_2 .⁶² No decisive change in peak intensity or significant shift of the main peak positions related to the tetragonal perovskite crystal structure is observed when choosing the green solvent system and an annealing temperature of 150 °C compared to the standard solvent system with 150 °C.

From the diffractograms, we conclude that the crystallographic properties of the perovskite layer fabricated by the green solvent system are similar to the one fabricated from a DMF:DMSO mixture which confirms the observation from the SEM images (Figure 3).

Spectral transmittance and reflectance measurements are conducted on annealed perovskite layers to evaluate calculated absorptance and compare the absorbing capacity of films fabricated from different solvent systems and annealing temperatures as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Spectral absorbance of double-cation perovskite layers blade coated on ITO/PTAA/SiO₂ NPs from a precursor solution in different solvent systems, namely 4:1 (vol:vol) DMF:DMSO mixture and DMSO, both annealed at temperatures of 100 °C or 150 °C.

Optical absorbance curves indicate in principle relatively similar trends for different samples. Notably, the typical strong, broad absorption of perovskite is observed also for samples from pure DMSO indicating no necessity of toxic DMF. Despite the interference effect due to potential perovskite thickness variations, the samples annealed at 150 °C indicate generally slightly higher absorption in the range from 580 nm to 760 nm compared to the ones with an annealing temperature of 100 °C. The sample fabricated from the pure DMSO solvent system and 150 °C annealing temperature shows the highest absorbance. The absorption edge of the signals of all thin films is formed between 750 nm and 770 nm which is attributed to the formation of the

FACsPbIBr perovskite.³² This fact correlates to the XRD measurements where the perovskite crystal structure was observed for both solvent systems and annealing temperatures as well.

Investigation of Elemental Composition of Perovskite Solar Cells. To investigate the chemical properties of the perovskite absorber and the elemental composition of the device stack, time-of-flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (TOF-SIMS) depth profiles are conducted on PSCs with perovskite layers utilizing both solvent systems and annealing temperatures (Figure S5).

The depth profiles reveal an expectable elemental composition through the device stacks. A homogeneous distribution of the main components of the double-cation perovskite, such as halide ions, indicated by the iodide (I) and bromide (Br) signals, and formamidinium (FA, CH₅N₂) ions, is identified throughout the perovskite bulk of all samples independently of the solvent system and annealing temperature. We did not observe a clear indication of any halide ion phase segregation, since halide signals run parallel to each other across the perovskite depth.⁹⁴ A slightly increased accumulation of the halide signals is observed at the BCP/Ag interface, whereas the signals of FA and lead (Pb) (not shown) are not concentrated at this interface. The reason for this fact might be the facile halide ion diffusion.⁹⁴ Cesium (Cs) in the absorber cannot be detected, since a cesium ion (Cs⁺) source is utilized as sputtering ion source to enable the removal of all layers in the complete cell stack. Moreover, negligible shifts of the graphs arise from differences in perovskite and ETL layer thicknesses of the samples as already presented in Figure S3.

From the TOF-SIMS study, we conclude that the chemical properties of the absorber layer and elemental composition in the solar cell are, independently of the annealing temperature, unaltered when choosing green DMSO instead of the standard DMF:DMSO mixture as perovskite precursor solution solvent.

Performance Analysis and Electrical Characterization of Perovskite Solar Cells. The perovskite layers deposited by one-step gas stream-assisted blade coating from a toxic and green solvent system are integrated in PSCs to compare their photovoltaic performance. Thereby, similar PCEs of up to over 16.5% on an active area of 0.24 cm² are reached.

As mentioned before, the recipes of both solvent systems were optimized separately resulting in different ideal process parameters of blade coating speed, delay time between wet layer deposition and gas stream-assisted perovskite conversion, and gas knife movement speed. This is clearly comprehensible because of the differences in rheology, especially in viscosity and vapor pressure (Table S1), of both solvent systems⁷⁵ requiring slower blade coating and gas knife movement speeds for pure DMSO by trend to reach wet layer thicknesses comparable to the case of the solvent mixture and appropriate drying, respectively. Furthermore, we emphasize, that the resulting perovskite thin film is fully homogenous on a 3 × 6 cm² substrate for the DMF:DMSO precursor solution without optimization of the gas knife stream direction (Figure 2), while this was not the case of the layer based on pure DMSO. Only if turning the gas knife 180 ° and blowing contrary to the blade coating direction, a perovskite film with a homogeneously covered area of over 95% of the substrate can be achieved. This fact is related to the DMSO rheology in conjunction with the intrinsic wet layer thickness gradient in blade coating direction because of missing continuous solution feeding. Moreover, we observed for both solvent systems that preventing turbulences induced by the gas knife is highly critical to achieve fast and sufficient quenching and, thus, homogenous perovskite films. For solar cell fabrication, 15 × 15 mm² substrates were cut out of the samples, which exhibit smooth perovskite surface and no milky appearance viewed from top side, which would be an indication for inadequate coverage of perovskite crystal grains.

PCE values of PSCs blade coated from a precursor solution in 4:1 (vol:vol) DMF:DMSO mixture and pure DMSO and annealed at temperatures of 100 °C and 150 °C are presented in Figure 5a. Figure S6a shows an overview of the statistic distribution of all characteristic photovoltaic device parameters of PCE, fill factor (FF), open circuit voltage (V_{OC}) and short-circuit current (J_{SC}). Current density-voltage ($J-V$) data of the champion devices of both solvent systems for this study is illustrated in Figure 5b.

Figure 5. (a) Statistic distribution of PCE in one device batch of PSCs with perovskite absorber blade coated from a precursor solution in different solvent systems (4:1 (vol:vol) DMF:DMSO mixture; DMSO), and annealed at different temperatures (100 °C; 150 °C). Shown values were measured in forward (up) and reverse (down) scan direction. (b) $J-V$ curves in both scan directions of champion photovoltaic devices of the two solvent systems (150 °C) for the complete study.

This batch comprises in total 48 devices, whereas 16 devices were annealed at 100 °C and 32 solar cells at 150 °C. From the evaluation of device performances with an annealing temperature of 150 °C, we conclude that with the green DMSO solvent system similar mean PCEs compared to the standard toxic DMF:DMSO mixture of circa 14% to 16% can be achieved. Furthermore, an

annealing temperature of 150 °C might be more favorable for reaching highest device performance of over 16% compared to 100 °C (close to 16%). Additionally, solar cells from DMSO and an annealing temperature of 100 °C exhibit decreased mean performance of close to 12% compared to its toxic counterpart (13%). These facts might be explained by the differences in crystal grain orientation (Figure S4). Moreover, the results of device performance shown here conform to the absorptance measurements displayed earlier (Figure 4). All devices show moderate hysteresis behavior caused by a small change in absolute V_{OC} of circa 10 mV but mainly due to an alteration in absolute FF of up to 4% as illustrated in Figure S6a. It should be noted that we did not observe the exact same trends in performance as a function of annealing temperature in another batch where coating speeds have been increased (Figure S7).

Steady-state measurements of PCE during maximum power point (MPP) tracking over a period of 5 min exhibit stable power output of corresponding representative solar cells (Figure S6b). The solar cells blade coated from a DMF:DMSO mixture demonstrate slightly more stable power output compared to the ones of pure DMSO which might be related to the different hysteresis (Figure 5a) and corresponding recombination behavior.

For our study, a similar champion perovskite solar cell PCE of 16.9% and 16.7% on an active area of 0.24 cm² was achieved in reverse scan direction for the DMF:DMSO and the DMSO solvent system, respectively, with an annealing temperature of 150 °C and slight hysteresis (Figure 5b). In forward scan direction, these devices showed PCEs of 16.3% with a FF of 74.5% and 15.5% with a FF of 72.1%, respectively. The data confirm the successful transfer of one-step double-cation perovskite blade coating from a toxic solvent system to a scalable deposition via a fully green precursor solvent.

External quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements reveal the relation of the spectral current generation of representative PSCs with perovskite absorber layers blade coated from a precursor solution in different solvent systems and annealed at both temperatures under an additional bias light (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Spectral evaluation of EQE of representative PSCs with double-cation perovskite absorber blade coated from a precursor solution in different solvent systems (4:1 (vol:vol) DMF:DMSO mixture; DMSO), and annealed at different temperatures (100 °C; 150 °C), measured with bias light.

EQE differences in the range between 580 nm and 760 nm are detected because of differing perovskite absorber thicknesses as illustrated in Figure S3 causing in some cases insufficient absorption of photons due to interference effects as mentioned before. Nevertheless, the integrated

J_{SC} values in Figure 6 precisely match with the ones extracted from $J-V$ curves (Figure S6a) in this study when a bias light is utilized during the measurement.

Figure S8 shows EQE measurements of the same photovoltaic devices without bias light. The EQE and integrated J_{SC} values are 5-10% relatively higher compared to the results in Figure 6 in all cases of the four parameter sets. This might be associated with recombination or hysteresis of the photovoltaic devices under light as demonstrated in Figure 5a due to ion migration.^{90,95} Without bias light, the integrated J_{SC} values exceed the ones obtained from $J-V$ curves by an absolute value of $\sim 1.5 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$. Since parasitic absorption of ITO/PTAA/SiO₂ NPs is expected to be the same for all samples, the differences in EQE might be mainly attributed to discrepancies in average crystal grain sizes (Figure 3e) and absorber thicknesses (Figure S3). The samples annealed at 150 °C exhibit in general larger grain sizes, which could reduce the charge recombination at grain boundaries leading to a higher EQE. The charge carrier diffusion lengths in the bulk might increase with larger grain sizes as well, thus, generally causing a higher quantum efficiency in the range of 400 nm to 600 nm.⁹⁶

The FACsPbIBr semiconductor band gap is calculated to be approximately 1.61 eV for the samples with an annealing temperature of 150 °C and 1.62 eV for cells with perovskite annealed at 100 °C independently from the solvent system which is in agreement with the measured V_{OC} and J_{SC} relation of corresponding solar cells (Figure S6a).

Device performances of solar cells fabricated from both solvent systems prove that the concept of blade coating double-cation perovskite from a green precursor solvent, instead of toxic DMF containing approaches, is extremely promising.

CONCLUSION

Harmful and polluting precursor solvents such as DMF hinder the transfer to scalable printing and large-scale production of PSCs by solution processing. For the first time, we here show inverted MA-free double-cation PSCs fabricated by one-step blade coating at low processing temperatures solely from DMSO. DMSO represents a green and environmentally safe precursor solvent, avoiding toxic solvent systems with DMF. By applying a blade coated SiO₂ NP wetting agent at the HTL/perovskite interface⁸⁰ and realizing sufficient DMSO quenching by gas stream-assisted drying, we address and master the two major challenges related to DMSO which explain why it has been rarely used as pure precursor solvent in literature for any type of perovskite or coating technique: (i) dewetting of the precursor solution on subjacent layers, especially on the highly hydrophobic PTAA, due to the high surface tension and viscosity of DMSO resulting in inhomogeneous perovskite films; (ii) its complex wet film quenching process due to a low vapor pressure and high boiling point of DMSO. Moreover, we compare trends in absorber grain size, morphology, crystallinity and elemental composition of samples fabricated from a toxic and green solvent system revealing analogous findings. Therefore, PSCs with 0.24 cm² active area blade coated from the pure green solvent DMSO achieve comparable device performance of up to 16.7% PCE to the ones from the toxic DMF:DMSO mixture (16.9%). Hence, we show that using toxic DMF is unnecessary.

In conclusion, the concept of replacing the commonly used toxic DMF as precursor solution solvent or as component in solvent mixtures by merely green DMSO discloses a pioneering route for perovskite deposition by scalable printing techniques such as blade coating. Consequently, this work provides a promising pathway to bring environmentally friendly solution processing of PSCs closer to industrial realization and application.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials. Substrates (soda lime float glass) with an indium-doped tin oxide (ITO) layer ($<15 \Omega \text{ sq}^{-1}$) with a thickness of 150 nm were purchased from VisionTek Systems. Lead iodide (PbI_2 , $>99.99\%$) and lead bromide (PbBr_2 , for perovskite precursor) were purchased from TCI. Cesium iodide (CsI , $>99.9995\%$), formamidinium iodide (FAI, anhydrous, $>99\%$), bathocuproine (BCP, sublimed grade, 99.99%), and solvents such as *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, anhydrous, 99.8%), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, anhydrous, $\geq 99.9\%$), and 1,2-dichlorobenzene (DCB, anhydrous, 99%), were ordered from Sigma-Aldrich. Ethanol (anhydrous) was provided by VWR. Poly(triaryl amine) (PTAA) was purchased from EM Index, whereas [6,6]-phenyl- C_{61} -butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM, 99.0%) was supplied by Solenne BV. All chemicals were utilized as received without further purification.

Nanoparticle (NP) Synthesis. The SiO_2 NPs in alcohol were synthesized as described in our previous report.⁸⁰ After stirring at 30°C for 3 hours, the stock solution exhibited a weight concentration in ethanol of 1.2 wt %. The NP stock dispersion was freshly diluted with ethanol to obtain the desired concentration of 0.9 wt %. The diameter of the NPs is approximately 20-30 nm. The stock solution was renewed at intervals of circa one to two months.

Perovskite Precursor Solution Preparation. A double-cation $\text{FA}_{0.83}\text{Cs}_{0.17}\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.87}\text{Br}_{0.13})_3$ perovskite was utilized in a concentration of 0.93 M. The precursor materials PbI_2 , CsI , PbBr_2 and FAI were dissolved in a DMF and DMSO mixture of 4:1 (vol:vol) ratio or solely in DMSO. After stirring at 70°C for 15 min, the solutions were cooled down to room temperature (RT), filtered and used after ~ 2 -3 hours.

Gas Stream-Assisted Blade Coating of Perovskite Film. Depositing the perovskite layer was performed via a blade coater (Automatic Research, TSC200) and commercial height adjustable

blade (Zehntner Testing Instruments, ZUA 2000 Universal Film Applicator). The process was performed inside a N₂-filled glovebox equipped with a pressure relief valve. The substrates are taped on the blade coater plate at the shorter edges during gas stream-assisted drying. The plate and substrate temperature were kept at 40 ± 5 °C. The gap between the blade and substrate was fixed at 100 μm, the coating speed at 18 mm s⁻¹ and at 7.5 mm s⁻¹ for the DMF:DMSO and DMSO recipe, respectively. A volume of 15 μL of each precursor solution (RT) was applied. Subsequent to a delay time until the first color change and of circa 35 s for the DMF:DMSO and DMSO recipe, respectively, the wet film was dried by a laminar gas stream of N₂ which changed its color to brown. During the delay time the blade was removed from the blade coater plate and the gas knife was installed. The gas stream (2.0 bar, 100 L min⁻¹, single inlet) was generated by a stainless steel air knife (Exair Super Air Knife, Eputec Drucklufttechnik) with a width of 152 mm and a 50 μm slit width. The air knife is mounted to a sled moving over the substrate at a speed of 9 mm s⁻¹ and 3.5 mm s⁻¹ for the DMF:DMSO and DMSO recipe, respectively. The stream direction was 45 ° to the substrate surface in blade coating direction and contrary to it for the DMF:DMSO and DMSO recipe, respectively. The distance from the gas knife outlet to the plate of the blade coater was ~4 mm. The resulting blowing speed of the N₂ gas stream was 30 to 35 m s⁻¹ which was measured by means of a flow meter. Subsequently, the substrates were transferred to a hot plate and were annealed at 100 °C or 150 °C for a period of 10 min in the glovebox.

Device Fabrication. 3 × 6 cm² sized laser patterned ITO substrates were cleaned by blowing with N₂. After treating the substrates with argon plasma at 100 W (0.38 mbar) for 2 min, a PTAA solution in dichlorobenzene with a concentration of 5 mg mL⁻¹ was deposited on ITO by blade coating in ambient conditions (19-22 °C, relative humidity 30-50%). The blade coater plate and substrate temperature were kept at 50 °C. A volume of 15 μL was utilized for each substrate. The

coating speed was 15 mm s^{-1} and the gap between the blade and substrate was adjusted to $80 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. Subsequently, the PTAA film was annealed at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min.

Afterward, a 0.9 wt % dispersion of SiO_2 NPs in ethanol was blade coated on the PTAA surface and dried as reported in our previous report.⁸⁰ For blade coating PTAA and the NP wetting agent, a commercially available blade (Zehntner Testing Instruments, ZUA 2000 Universal Film Applicator) on a blade coater (Zehntner Testing Instruments, ZAA 2300 Automatic Film Applicator) was used.

After deposition of the NPs, the substrates were transferred into a N_2 -filled glovebox. The perovskite film was deposited via gas stream-assisted blade coating described above. Thereafter, the $3 \times 6 \text{ cm}^2$ substrates were removed from the glovebox and were cut in pieces of $15 \times 15 \text{ mm}^2$. Next, the ETLs of PCBM and BCP were spin coated in a spin coater (MBraun, MB-SC-200) inside a N_2 -filled glovebox. A PCBM solution with a concentration of 40 mg mL^{-1} in dichlorobenzene was spin coated by static droplet deposition via a recipe with two steps comprising 1000 rpm for 30 s and 2000 rpm for 5 s. During processing, the solution was kept stirring at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and was applied hot. For each substrate, a volume of $30 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$ was used. Subsequently, $40 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of a BCP solution with a concentration of 1 mg mL^{-1} in ethanol was spin coated dynamically on top of PCBM at 3000 rpm for 34 s.

A 120 nm thick Ag electrode was thermally evaporated under high vacuum conditions ($<10^{-6} \text{ mbar}$) through a metal aperture mask to finalize the devices and define a 0.24 cm^2 device active area.

Device Characterization. The performance of photovoltaic devices was measured with a source meter (Keithley, 2400) at a scan speed of 0.28 V s^{-1} under illumination of standard test conditions by a class AAA solar simulator (Wacom, WXS-90S-L2 Super Solar Simulator) in ambient air.

With the aid of a silicon cell, the solar simulator was calibrated to 1000 W m^{-2} (AM 1.5G). The measurement range was from -0.2 V to $+1.5 \text{ V}$ and vice versa, respectively. The presented solar cells were annealed at $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 s to 60 s and cooled down to RT before measuring. No other treatments such as light soaking or biasing were applied to the devices before recording the J - V characteristics. During the measurement, the PSCs were kept at $25.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The steady-state measurement of PCE during dynamic MPP tracking was performed via continuous adjustment of the applied voltage.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). To obtain top-view and cross-section SEM images, a scanning electron microscope (Zeiss, Gemini 2 Crossbeam 550) with an in-lens detector was utilized.

Time-of-flight Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (TOF-SIMS). The depth profile measurements of solar cells were conducted with a TOF-SIMS setup (ION-TOF GmbH, TOF-SIMS 5). As an analytical source, pulsed Bi_3^+ primary ions from a 30 keV liquid-metal ion gun were utilized, whereas a 1 keV Cs^+ source was used as a sputtering ion source. The TOF-SIMS depth analysis was performed on a $50 \times 50 \text{ } \mu\text{m}^2$ area in the so-called spectrometry mode inside a sputtering crater with a size of $200 \times 200 \text{ } \mu\text{m}^2$.

External Quantum Efficiency (EQE). An EQE system (Bentham, PVE300) was utilized without and with bias light (corresponding to circa 0.25 sun) to determine the EQE data. The spectral range of the measurements was from 300 nm to 900 nm. A standardized silicon photodiode (300-1100 nm) was used to calibrate the setup prior to the measurements. The area of the measurement spot was 0.05 cm^2 .

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD). The XRD data (2θ scan, 10-70 °) was collected by means of a diffractometer (Panalytical, Empyrean) with a Cu $K\alpha$ radiation source in Bragg-Brentano geometry. Acceleration voltage and current were set to 40 V and 40 μ A, respectively.

Absorptance. The absorptance (A) spectra were calculated by using measured transmittance (T) and reflectance (R) signals ($A=1-T-R$). A spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer, Lambda 900) was used to capture the data. The incidence of light was from the sample side.

Crystal Grain Size Characterization. The evaluation of the SEM images and measuring the crystal grain size distribution was performed via the program ImageJ.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. The Supporting Information is available free of charge on ACS Publications website at DOI: 10.1021/.

Overview of physical characteristics of precursor solution solvents for PSC production (Table S1); photographical image of perovskite film on Glass/ITO/PTAA without and with SiO₂ NPs at the PTAA/perovskite interface (Figure S1); SEM top-view images of perovskite layers blade coated from a precursor solution in a toxic and green solvent system and annealed at different temperatures (Figure S2); SEM cross-section images of device stacks with perovskite layer blade coated from a precursor solution in a toxic and green solvent system and annealed at different temperatures (Figure S3); XRD patterns of perovskite layers blade coated from a precursor solution in a toxic and green solvent system and annealed at different temperatures (Figure S4); TOF-SIMS depth profiles through device stack with perovskite absorber blade coated from a precursor solution in a toxic and green solvent system and annealed at different temperatures (Figure S5); statistic distribution of photovoltaic parameters of PSCs with perovskite absorber

blade coated from a precursor solution in a toxic and green solvent system and annealed at different temperatures (Figure S6); statistic distribution of photovoltaic parameters of PSCs with perovskite absorber blade coated with higher coating speeds from a precursor solution in a toxic and green solvent system and annealed at different temperatures (Figure S7); Spectral evaluation of EQE without bias light of PSCs with perovskite absorber blade coated from a precursor solution in a toxic and green solvent system and annealed at different temperatures (Figure S8) (PDF)

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

*E-Mail: johannes.kueffner@zsw-bw.de

*E-Mail: erik.ahlsvede@zsw-bw.de

ORCID

Johannes Küffner: 0000-0002-4762-4764

Erik Ahlsvede: 0000-0001-8782-136X

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was funded under H2020-EU.3.3.2 by the European Commission within the project 850937 (PERCISTAND) and supported by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi) under the contract number 03EE1038A (CAPITANO). J.K. acknowledges

Daniela Müller for SEM measurements. Further, J.K. acknowledges the Karlsruhe School of Optics & Photonics (KSOP).

REFERENCES

- (1) Kojima, A.; Teshima, K.; Shirai, Y.; Miyasaka, T. Organometal Halide Perovskites as Visible-Light Sensitizers for Photovoltaic Cells. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131* (17), 6050–6051. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja809598r>.
- (2) Best Research-Cell Efficiency Chart | Photovoltaic Research | NREL <https://www.nrel.gov/pv/cell-efficiency.html> (accessed Apr 22, 2021).
- (3) Liu, K.; Liang, Q.; Qin, M.; Shen, D.; Yin, H.; Ren, Z.; Zhang, Y.; Zhang, H.; Fong, P. W. K.; Wu, Z.; Huang, J.; Hao, J.; Zheng, Z.; So, S. K.; Lee, C.; Lu, X.; Li, G. Zwitterionic-Surfactant-Assisted Room-Temperature Coating of Efficient Perovskite Solar Cells. *Joule* **2020**, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2020.09.011>.
- (4) Hu, H.; Ren, Z.; Fong, P. W. K.; Qin, M.; Liu, D.; Lei, D.; Lu, X.; Li, G. Room-Temperature Meniscus Coating of >20% Perovskite Solar Cells: A Film Formation Mechanism Investigation. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2019**, *29* (25), 1900092. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201900092>.
- (5) Deng, Y.; Van Brackle, C. H.; Dai, X.; Zhao, J.; Chen, B.; Huang, J. Tailoring Solvent Coordination for High-Speed, Room-Temperature Blading of Perovskite Photovoltaic Films. *Sci. Adv.* **2019**, *5* (12), eaax7537. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aax7537>.
- (6) Li, D.; Zhang, D.; Lim, K.; Hu, Y.; Rong, Y.; Mei, A.; Park, N.; Han, H. A Review on Scaling Up Perovskite Solar Cells. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2020**, 2008621.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202008621>.

- (7) Howard, I. A.; Abzieher, T.; Hossain, I. M.; Eggers, H.; Schackmar, F.; Ternes, S.; Richards, B. S.; Lemmer, U.; Paetzold, U. W. Coated and Printed Perovskites for Photovoltaic Applications. *Adv. Mater.* **2019**, *31* (26), 1806702. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201806702>.
- (8) Swartwout, R.; Hoerantner, M. T.; Bulović, V. Scalable Deposition Methods for Large-Area Production of Perovskite Thin Films. *ENERGY Environ. Mater.* **2019**, *2* (2), 119–145. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eem2.12043>.
- (9) Cai, H.; Liang, X.; Ye, X.; Su, J.; Guan, J.; Yang, J.; Liu, Y.; Zhou, X.; Han, R.; Ni, J.; Li, J.; Zhang, J. High Efficiency over 20% of Perovskite Solar Cells by Spray Coating via a Simple Process. *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *0* (1), acsaem.0c01129. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.0c01129>.
- (10) Huang, H.; Shi, J.; Zhu, L.; Li, D.; Luo, Y.; Meng, Q. Two-Step Ultrasonic Spray Deposition of CH₃NH₃PbI₃ for Efficient and Large-Area Perovskite Solar Cell. *Nano Energy* **2016**, *27*, 352–358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2016.07.026>.
- (11) Tang, S.; Deng, Y.; Zheng, X.; Bai, Y.; Fang, Y.; Dong, Q.; Wei, H.; Huang, J. Composition Engineering in Doctor-Blading of Perovskite Solar Cells. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2017**, *7* (18), 1700302. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201700302>.
- (12) Wu, W.; Yang, Z.; Rudd, P. N.; Shao, Y.; Dai, X.; Wei, H.; Zhao, J.; Fang, Y.; Wang, Q.; Liu, Y.; Deng, Y.; Xiao, X.; Feng, Y.; Huang, J. Bilateral Alkylamine for Suppressing Charge Recombination and Improving Stability in Blade-Coated Perovskite Solar Cells. *Sci.*

Adv. **2019**, 5 (3), eaav8925. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aav8925>.

- (13) Li, J.; Munir, R.; Fan, Y.; Niu, T.; Liu, Y.; Zhong, Y.; Yang, Z.; Tian, Y.; Liu, B.; Sun, J.; Smilgies, D.-M.; Thoroddsen, S.; Amassian, A.; Zhao, K.; Liu, S. (Frank). Phase Transition Control for High-Performance Blade-Coated Perovskite Solar Cells. *Joule* **2018**, 2 (7), 1313–1330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2018.04.011>.
- (14) Lee, D.-K.; Jeong, D.-N.; Ahn, T. K.; Park, N.-G. Precursor Engineering for a Large-Area Perovskite Solar Cell with >19% Efficiency. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2019**, 4 (10), 2393–2401. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenergylett.9b01735>.
- (15) He, M.; Li, B.; Cui, X.; Jiang, B.; He, Y.; Chen, Y.; O’Neil, D.; Szymanski, P.; El-Sayed, M. A.; Huang, J.; Lin, Z. Meniscus-Assisted Solution Printing of Large-Grained Perovskite Films for High-Efficiency Solar Cells. *Nat. Commun.* **2017**, 8 (1), 16045. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms16045>.
- (16) Lee, D.-K.; Lim, K.-S.; Lee, J.-W.; Park, N.-G. Scalable Perovskite Coating via Anti-Solvent-Free Lewis Acid-Base Adduct Engineering for Efficient Perovskite Solar Modules. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2021**, 9 (5), 3018–3028. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0TA10366G>.
- (17) Lim, K.-S.; Lee, D.-K.; Lee, J.-W.; Park, N.-G. 17% Efficient Perovskite Solar Mini-Module via Hexamethylphosphoramide (HMPA)-Adduct-Based Large-Area D-Bar Coating. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2020**, 8 (18), 9345–9354. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0TA02017F>.
- (18) Jinzhao, L.; Janardan, D.; Oleksandra, S.; Daniel, T.; Rahim, M.; Unger, E. 20.8% Slot-Die Coated MAPbI₃ Perovskite Solar Cells by Optimal DMSO-Content and Age of 2-ME

- Based Precursor Inks. **2020**. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-93765/v1>.
- (19) Lee, D.; Jung, Y.-S.; Heo, Y.-J.; Lee, S.; Hwang, K.; Jeon, Y.-J.; Kim, J.-E.; Park, J.; Jung, G. Y.; Kim, D.-Y. Slot-Die Coated Perovskite Films Using Mixed Lead Precursors for Highly Reproducible and Large-Area Solar Cells. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2018**, *10* (18), 16133–16139. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b02549>.
- (20) Burkitt, D.; Swartwout, R.; McGettrick, J.; Greenwood, P.; Beynon, D.; Brenes, R.; Bulović, V.; Watson, T. Acetonitrile Based Single Step Slot-Die Compatible Perovskite Ink for Flexible Photovoltaics. *RSC Adv.* **2019**, *9* (64), 37415–37423. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9RA06631D>.
- (21) Vijayan, A.; Johansson, M. B.; Svanström, S.; Cappel, U. B.; Rensmo, H.; Boschloo, G. Simple Method for Efficient Slot-Die Coating of MAPbI₃ Perovskite Thin Films in Ambient Air Conditions. *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *3* (5), 4331–4337. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.0c00039>.
- (22) Li, P.; Liang, C.; Bao, B.; Li, Y.; Hu, X.; Wang, Y.; Zhang, Y.; Li, F.; Shao, G.; Song, Y. Inkjet Manipulated Homogeneous Large Size Perovskite Grains for Efficient and Large-Area Perovskite Solar Cells. *Nano Energy* **2018**, *46*, 203–211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.01.049>.
- (23) Schackmar, F.; Eggers, H.; Frericks, M.; Richards, B. S.; Lemmer, U.; Hernandez-Sosa, G.; Paetzold, U. W. Perovskite Solar Cells with All-Inkjet-Printed Absorber and Charge Transport Layers. *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **2020**, 2000271. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admt.202000271>.

- (24) Eggers, H.; Schackmar, F.; Abzieher, T.; Sun, Q.; Lemmer, U.; Vaynzof, Y.; Richards, B. S.; Hernandez-Sosa, G.; Paetzold, U. W. Inkjet-Printed Micrometer-Thick Perovskite Solar Cells with Large Columnar Grains. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *10* (6), 1903184. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201903184>.
- (25) Dou, B.; Whitaker, J. B.; Bruening, K.; Moore, D. T.; Wheeler, L. M.; Ryter, J.; Breslin, N. J.; Berry, J. J.; Garner, S. M.; Barnes, F. S.; Shaheen, S. E.; Tassone, C. J.; Zhu, K.; van Hest, M. F. A. M. Roll-to-Roll Printing of Perovskite Solar Cells. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2018**, *3* (10), 2558–2565. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acseenergylett.8b01556>.
- (26) Burkitt, D.; Patidar, R.; Greenwood, P.; Hooper, K.; McGettrick, J.; Dimitrov, S.; Colombo, M.; Stoichkov, V.; Richards, D.; Beynon, D.; Davies, M.; Watson, T. Roll-to-Roll Slot-Die Coated P-I-N Perovskite Solar Cells Using Acetonitrile Based Single Step Perovskite Solvent System. *Sustain. Energy Fuels* **2020**, No. c, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0SE00460J>.
- (27) Angmo, D.; DeLuca, G.; Scully, A. D.; Chesman, A. S. R.; Seeber, A.; Zuo, C.; Vak, D.; Bach, U.; Gao, M. A Lab-to-Fab Study toward Roll-to-Roll Fabrication of Reproducible Perovskite Solar Cells under Ambient Room Conditions. *Cell Reports Phys. Sci.* **2021**, 100293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xcrp.2020.100293>.
- (28) Correa-Baena, J.-P.; Abate, A.; Saliba, M.; Tress, W.; Jesper Jacobsson, T.; Grätzel, M.; Hagfeldt, A. The Rapid Evolution of Highly Efficient Perovskite Solar Cells. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2017**, *10* (3), 710–727. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6EE03397K>.
- (29) Saliba, M.; Matsui, T.; Seo, J.-Y.; Domanski, K.; Correa-Baena, J.-P.; Nazeeruddin, M. K.; Zakeeruddin, S. M.; Tress, W.; Abate, A.; Hagfeldt, A.; Grätzel, M. Cesium-Containing

- Triple Cation Perovskite Solar Cells: Improved Stability, Reproducibility and High Efficiency. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2016**, *9* (6), 1989–1997. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5EE03874J>.
- (30) Saliba, M.; Matsui, T.; Domanski, K.; Seo, J.-Y.; Ummadisingu, A.; Zakeeruddin, S. M.; Correa-Baena, J.-P.; Tress, W. R.; Abate, A.; Hagfeldt, A.; Gratzel, M. Incorporation of Rubidium Cations into Perovskite Solar Cells Improves Photovoltaic Performance. *Science (80-.)*. **2016**, *354* (6309), 206–209. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aah5557>.
- (31) Schwenzler, J. A.; Hellmann, T.; Nejdand, B. A.; Hu, H.; Abzieher, T.; Schackmar, F.; Hossain, I. M.; Fassel, P.; Mayer, T.; Jaegermann, W.; Lemmer, U.; Paetzold, U. W. Thermal Stability and Cation Composition of Hybrid Organic-Inorganic Perovskites. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2021**, acsami.1c01547. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.1c01547>.
- (32) McMeekin, D. P.; Sadoughi, G.; Rehman, W.; Eperon, G. E.; Saliba, M.; Horantner, M. T.; Haghighirad, A.; Sakai, N.; Korte, L.; Rech, B.; Johnston, M. B.; Herz, L. M.; Snaith, H. J. A Mixed-Cation Lead Mixed-Halide Perovskite Absorber for Tandem Solar Cells. *Science (80-.)*. **2016**, *351* (6269), 151–155. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aad5845>.
- (33) Zhong, J.; Wu, W.; Ding, L.; Kuang, D. Blade-Coating Perovskite Films with Diverse Compositions for Efficient Photovoltaics. *ENERGY Environ. Mater.* **2020**, eem2.12118. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eem2.12118>.
- (34) Zeng, L.; Chen, S.; Forberich, K.; Brabec, C. J.; Mai, Y.; Guo, F. Controlling the Crystallization Dynamics of Photovoltaic Perovskite Layers on Larger-Area Coatings. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2020**, *13* (12), 4666–4690. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0EE02575E>.

- (35) Yang, F.; Dong, L.; Jang, D.; Tam, K. C.; Zhang, K.; Li, N.; Guo, F.; Li, C.; Arrive, C.; Bertrand, M.; Brabec, C. J.; Egelhaaf, H. Fully Solution Processed Pure α -Phase Formamidinium Lead Iodide Perovskite Solar Cells for Scalable Production in Ambient Condition. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *10* (42), 2001869. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202001869>.
- (36) Guo, F.; He, W.; Qiu, S.; Wang, C.; Liu, X.; Forberich, K.; Brabec, C. J.; Mai, Y. Sequential Deposition of High-Quality Photovoltaic Perovskite Layers via Scalable Printing Methods. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2019**, *29* (24), 1900964. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201900964>.
- (37) Guo, F.; Qiu, S.; Hu, J.; Wang, H.; Cai, B.; Li, J.; Yuan, X.; Liu, X.; Forberich, K.; Brabec, C. J.; Mai, Y. A Generalized Crystallization Protocol for Scalable Deposition of High-Quality Perovskite Thin Films for Photovoltaic Applications. *Adv. Sci.* **2019**, *6* (17), 1901067. <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.201901067>.
- (38) Hu, J.; Wang, C.; Qiu, S.; Zhao, Y.; Gu, E.; Zeng, L.; Yang, Y.; Li, C.; Liu, X.; Forberich, K.; Brabec, C. J.; Nazeeruddin, M. K.; Mai, Y.; Guo, F. Spontaneously Self-Assembly of a 2D/3D Heterostructure Enhances the Efficiency and Stability in Printed Perovskite Solar Cells. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *10* (17), 2000173. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202000173>.
- (39) Gharibzadeh, S.; Abdollahi Nejand, B.; Jakoby, M.; Abzieher, T.; Hauschild, D.; Moghadamzadeh, S.; Schwenzer, J. A.; Brenner, P.; Schmager, R.; Haghighirad, A. A.; Weinhardt, L.; Lemmer, U.; Richards, B. S.; Howard, I. A.; Paetzold, U. W. Record Open-Circuit Voltage Wide-Bandgap Perovskite Solar Cells Utilizing 2D/3D Perovskite Heterostructure. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2019**, *9* (21), 1803699.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201803699>.

- (40) Prochowicz, D.; Yadav, P.; Saliba, M.; Kubicki, D. J.; Tavakoli, M. M.; Zakeeruddin, S. M.; Lewiński, J.; Emsley, L.; Grätzel, M. One-Step Mechanochemical Incorporation of an Insoluble Cesium Additive for High Performance Planar Heterojunction Solar Cells. *Nano Energy* **2018**, *49*, 523–528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.05.010>.
- (41) Aamir, M.; Adhikari, T.; Sher, M.; Revaprasadu, N.; Khalid, W.; Akhtar, J.; Nunzi, J.-M. Fabrication of Planar Heterojunction CsPbBr₂ I Perovskite Solar Cells Using ZnO as an Electron Transport Layer and Improved Solar Energy Conversion Efficiency. *New J. Chem.* **2018**, *42* (17), 14104–14110. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8NJ02238K>.
- (42) Ono, L. K.; Park, N.-G.; Zhu, K.; Huang, W.; Qi, Y. Perovskite Solar Cells-Towards Commercialization. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2017**, *2* (8), 1749–1751. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acseenergylett.7b00517>.
- (43) Swartwout, R.; Patidir, R.; Belliveau, E.; Dou, B.; Beynon, D.; Greenwood, P.; Moody, N.; DeQuilettes, D. W.; Bawendi, M.; Watson, T. M.; Bulovic, V. Predicting Low Toxicity and Scalable Solvent Systems for High Speed Roll-to-Roll Perovskite Manufacturing. **2020**. <https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv.13221851.v1>.
- (44) Zhang, M.; Xin, D.; Zheng, X.; Chen, Q.; Zhang, W.-H. Toward Greener Solution Processing of Perovskite Solar Cells. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2020**, *8* (35), 13126–13138. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.0c04289>.
- (45) Capello, C.; Fischer, U.; Hungerbühler, K. What Is a Green Solvent? A Comprehensive Framework for the Environmental Assessment of Solvents. *Green Chem.* **2007**, *9* (9), 927.

<https://doi.org/10.1039/b617536h>.

- (46) Huang, S.-H.; Tian, K.; Huang, H.-C.; Li, C.; Chu, W.; Lee, K.; Huang, Y.; Su, W.-F. Controlling the Morphology and Interface of the Perovskite Layer for Scalable High-Efficiency Solar Cells Fabricated Using Green Solvents and Blade Coating in an Ambient Environment. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2020**, *12* (23), 26041–26049. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.0c06211>.
- (47) Gardner, K. L.; Tait, J. G.; Merckx, T.; Qiu, W.; Paetzold, U. W.; Kootstra, L.; Jaysankar, M.; Gehlhaar, R.; Cheyins, D.; Heremans, P.; Poortmans, J. Nonhazardous Solvent Systems for Processing Perovskite Photovoltaics. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2016**, *6* (14), 1600386. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201600386>.
- (48) Wang, J.; Di Giacomo, F.; Bröls, J.; Gortler, H.; Katsouras, I.; Groen, P.; Janssen, R. A. J.; Andriessen, R.; Galagan, Y. Highly Efficient Perovskite Solar Cells Using Non-Toxic Industry Compatible Solvent System. *Sol. RRL* **2017**, *1* (11), 1700091. <https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.201700091>.
- (49) Babaei, A.; Albero-Blanquer, L.; Igual-Muñoz, A. M.; Pérez-Del-Rey, D.; Sessolo, M.; Bolink, H. J.; Tadmouri, R. Hansen Theory Applied to the Identification of Nonhazardous Solvents for Hybrid Perovskite Thin-Films Processing. *Polyhedron* **2018**, *147*, 9–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.poly.2018.03.003>.
- (50) Öz, S.; Burschka, J.; Jung, E.; Bhattacharjee, R.; Fischer, T.; Mettenböcker, A.; Wang, H.; Mathur, S. Protic Ionic Liquid Assisted Solution Processing of Lead Halide Perovskites with Water, Alcohols and Acetonitrile. *Nano Energy* **2018**, *51*, 632–638. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.07.005>.

- (51) Bi, Z.; Rodríguez-Martínez, X.; Aranda, C.; Pascual-San-José, E.; Goñi, A. R.; Campoy-Quiles, M.; Xu, X.; Guerrero, A. Defect Tolerant Perovskite Solar Cells from Blade Coated Non-Toxic Solvents. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2018**, *6* (39), 19085–19093. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8TA06771F>.
- (52) Worsley, C.; Raptis, D.; Meroni, S.; Doolin, A.; Garcia-Rodriguez, R.; Davies, M.; Watson, T. γ -Valerolactone: A Nontoxic Green Solvent for Highly Stable Printed Mesoporous Perovskite Solar Cells. *Energy Technol.* **2021**, 2100312. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ente.202100312>.
- (53) Doolin, A. J.; Charles, R. G.; De Castro, C. S. P.; Rodriguez, R. G.; Péan, E. V.; Patidar, R.; Dunlop, T.; Charbonneau, C.; Watson, T.; Davies, M. L. Sustainable Solvent Selection for the Manufacture of Methylammonium Lead Triiodide (MAPbI₃) Perovskite Solar Cells. *Green Chem.* **2021**, *23* (6), 2471–2486. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1GC00079A>.
- (54) Tang, M.; Fan, Y.; Barrit, D.; Chang, X.; Dang, H. X.; Li, R.; Wang, K.; Smilgies, D.; Liu, S. F.; De Wolf, S.; Anthopoulos, T. D.; Zhao, K.; Amassian, A. Ambient Blade Coating of Mixed Cation, Mixed Halide Perovskites without Dripping: In Situ Investigation and Highly Efficient Solar Cells. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2020**, *8* (3), 1095–1104. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9TA12890E>.
- (55) Wu, W.-Q.; Rudd, P. N.; Ni, Z.; Van Brackle, C. H.; Wei, H.; Wang, Q.; Ecker, B. R.; Gao, Y.; Huang, J. Reducing Surface Halide Deficiency for Efficient and Stable Iodide-Based Perovskite Solar Cells. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142* (8), 3989–3996. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.9b13418>.
- (56) Fong, P. W.; Hu, H.; Ren, Z.; Liu, K.; Cui, L.; Bi, T.; Liang, Q.; Wu, Z.; Hao, J.; Li, G.

- Printing High-Efficiency Perovskite Solar Cells in High-Humidity Ambient Environment-An In Situ Guided Investigation. *Adv. Sci.* **2021**, 2003359. <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.202003359>.
- (57) Castriotta, L. A.; Matteocci, F.; Vesce, L.; Cinà, L.; Agresti, A.; Pescetelli, S.; Ronconi, A.; Löffler, M.; Stylianakis, M. M.; Di Giacomo, F.; Mariani, P.; Stefanelli, M.; Speller, E. M.; Alfano, A.; Paci, B.; Generosi, A.; Di Fonzo, F.; Petrozza, A.; Rellinghaus, B.; Kymakis, E.; Di Carlo, A. Air-Processed Infrared-Annealed Printed Methylammonium-Free Perovskite Solar Cells and Modules Incorporating Potassium-Doped Graphene Oxide as an Interlayer. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2021**, acsami.0c18920. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.0c18920>.
- (58) Li, H.; Bu, T.; Li, J.; Lin, Z.; Pan, J.; Li, Q.; Zhang, X.-L.; Ku, Z.; Cheng, Y.-B.; Huang, F. Ink Engineering for Blade Coating FA-Dominated Perovskites in Ambient Air for Efficient Solar Cells and Modules. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2021**, acsami.1c00900. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.1c00900>.
- (59) Li, N.; Liu, J.; Li, C.; Li, Y.; Jia, J.; Wu, Y.; Yu, H.; Yuan, B.; Cao, B. Zwitterion-Stabilizing Scalable Bladed α -Phase Cs_{0.1}FA_{0.9}PbI₃ Films for Efficient Inverted Planar Perovskite Solar Cells. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2020**, 8 (18), 7020–7030. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.0c00417>.
- (60) Dai, X.; Deng, Y.; Van Brackle, C. H.; Chen, S.; Rudd, P. N.; Xiao, X.; Lin, Y.; Chen, B.; Huang, J. Scalable Fabrication of Efficient Perovskite Solar Modules on Flexible Glass Substrates. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2020**, 10 (1), 1903108. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201903108>.

- (61) Chen, B.; Yu, Z. J.; Manzoor, S.; Wang, S.; Weigand, W.; Yu, Z.; Yang, G.; Ni, Z.; Dai, X.; Holman, Z. C.; Huang, J. Blade-Coated Perovskites on Textured Silicon for 26%-Efficient Monolithic Perovskite/Silicon Tandem Solar Cells. *Joule* **2020**, *4* (4), 850–864. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2020.01.008>.
- (62) Deng, Y.; Xu, S.; Chen, S.; Xiao, X.; Zhao, J.; Huang, J. Defect Compensation in Formamidinium-Caesium Perovskites for Highly Efficient Solar Mini-Modules with Improved Photostability. *Nat. Energy* **2021**, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-021-00831-8>.
- (63) Wilk, B.; Öz, S.; Radicchi, E.; Ünlü, F.; Ahmad, T.; Herman, A. P.; Nunzi, F.; Mathur, S.; Kudrawiec, R.; Wojciechowski, K. Green Solvent-Based Perovskite Precursor Development for Ink-Jet Printed Flexible Solar Cells. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2021**, [acssuschemeng.0c09208](https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.0c09208). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.0c09208>.
- (64) Park, N.-G. Green Solvent for Perovskite Solar Cell Production. *Nat. Sustain.* **2020**, 3–4. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-00647-6>.
- (65) Byrne, F. P.; Jin, S.; Paggiola, G.; Petchey, T. H. M.; Clark, J. H.; Farmer, T. J.; Hunt, A. J.; Robert McElroy, C.; Sherwood, J. Tools and Techniques for Solvent Selection: Green Solvent Selection Guides. *Sustain. Chem. Process.* **2016**, *4* (1), 7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40508-016-0051-z>.
- (66) Vidal, R.; Alberola-Borràs, J.-A.; Habisreutinger, S. N.; Gimeno-Molina, J.-L.; Moore, D. T.; Schloemer, T. H.; Mora-Seró, I.; Berry, J. J.; Luther, J. M. Assessing Health and Environmental Impacts of Solvents for Producing Perovskite Solar Cells. *Nat. Sustain.* **2021**, *4* (3), 277–285. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-00645-8>.

- (67) Vidal, R.; Alberola-Borràs, J.; Sánchez-Pantoja, N.; Mora-Seró, I. Comparison of Perovskite Solar Cells with Other Photovoltaics Technologies from the Point of View of Life Cycle Assessment. *Adv. Energy Sustain. Res.* **2021**, 2000088. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aesr.202000088>.
- (68) Hamill, J. C.; Schwartz, J.; Loo, Y.-L. Influence of Solvent Coordination on Hybrid Organic-Inorganic Perovskite Formation. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2018**, 3 (1), 92–97. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acseenergylett.7b01057>.
- (69) Galagan, Y.; Di Giacomo, F.; Gortler, H.; Kirchner, G.; de Vries, I.; Andriessen, R.; Groen, P. Roll-to-Roll Slot Die Coated Perovskite for Efficient Flexible Solar Cells. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2018**, 8 (32), 1801935. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201801935>.
- (70) Geppert-Rybczyńska, M.; Lehmann, J. K.; Safarov, J.; Heintz, A. Thermodynamic Surface Properties of [BMIm][NTf₂] or [EMIm][NTf₂] Binary Mixtures with Tetrahydrofuran, Acetonitrile or Dimethylsulfoxide. *J. Chem. Thermodyn.* **2013**, 62, 104–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jct.2013.02.021>.
- (71) Isikgor, F. H.; Subbiah, A. S.; Eswaran, M. K.; Howells, C. T.; Babayigit, A.; De Bastiani, M.; Yengel, E.; Liu, J.; Furlan, F.; Harrison, G. T.; Zhumagali, S.; Khan, J. I.; Laquai, F.; Anthopoulos, T. D.; McCulloch, I.; Schwingenschlögl, U.; De Wolf, S. Scaling-up Perovskite Solar Cells on Hydrophobic Surfaces. *Nano Energy* **2020**, 105633. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2020.105633>.
- (72) Jeong, D.-N.; Lee, D.-K.; Seo, S.; Lim, S. Y.; Zhang, Y.; Shin, H.; Cheong, H.; Park, N.-G. Perovskite Cluster-Containing Solution for Scalable D-Bar Coating toward High-Throughput Perovskite Solar Cells. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2019**, 4 (5), 1189–1195.

<https://doi.org/10.1021/acseenergylett.9b00042>.

- (73) Shargaieva, O.; Näsström, H.; Smith, J. A.; Töbrens, D.; Munir, R.; Unger, E. Hybrid Perovskite Crystallization from Binary Solvent Mixtures: Interplay of Evaporation Rate and Binding Strength of Solvents. *Mater. Adv.* **2020**, *1* (9), 3314–3321. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0MA00815J>.
- (74) Ozaki, M.; Shimazaki, A.; Jung, M.; Nakaike, Y.; Maruyama, N.; Yakumar, S.; Rafieh, A. I.; Sasamori, T.; Tokitoh, N.; Ekanayake, P.; Murata, Y.; Murdey, R.; Wakamiya, A. A Purified, Solvent-Intercalated Precursor Complex for Wide-Process-Window Fabrication of Efficient Perovskite Solar Cells and Modules. *Angew. Chemie* **2019**, *131* (28), 9489–9493. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ange.201902235>.
- (75) Burkitt, D.; Searle, J.; Worsley, D.; Watson, T. Sequential Slot-Die Deposition of Perovskite Solar Cells Using Dimethylsulfoxide Lead Iodide Ink. *Materials (Basel)*. **2018**, *11* (11), 2106. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma11112106>.
- (76) Masi, S.; Echeverría-Arrondo, C.; Salim, K. M. M.; Ngo, T. T.; Mendez, P. F.; López-Fraguas, E.; Macias-Pinilla, D. F.; Planelles, J.; Climente, J. I.; Mora-Seró, I. Chemi-Structural Stabilization of Formamidinium Lead Iodide Perovskite by Using Embedded Quantum Dots. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2020**, *5* (2), 418–427. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acseenergylett.9b02450>.
- (77) Seo, Y.-H.; Kim, E.-C.; Cho, S.-P.; Kim, S.-S.; Na, S.-I. High-Performance Planar Perovskite Solar Cells: Influence of Solvent upon Performance. *Appl. Mater. Today* **2017**, *9*, 598–604. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmt.2017.11.003>.

- (78) Giuri, A.; Masi, S.; Listorti, A.; Gigli, G.; Colella, S.; Esposito Corcione, C.; Rizzo, A. Polymeric Rheology Modifier Allows Single-Step Coating of Perovskite Ink for Highly Efficient and Stable Solar Cells. *Nano Energy* **2018**, *54*, 400–408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.10.039>.
- (79) Zhang, Y.; Chen, M.; Zhou, Y.; Li, W.; Lee, Y.; Kanda, H.; Gao, X.; Hu, R.; Brooks, K. G.; Zia, R.; Kinge, S.; Padture, N. P.; Nazeeruddin, M. K. The Synergism of DMSO and Diethyl Ether for Highly Reproducible and Efficient MA 0.5 FA 0.5 PbI₃ Perovskite Solar Cells. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *10* (29), 2001300. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202001300>.
- (80) Küffner, J.; Wahl, T.; Schultes, M.; Hanisch, J.; Zillner, J.; Ahlswede, E.; Powalla, M. Nanoparticle Wetting Agent for Gas Stream-Assisted Blade-Coated Inverted Perovskite Solar Cells and Modules. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2020**, *12* (47), 52678–52690. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.0c15428>.
- (81) Schultes, M.; Giesbrecht, N.; Küffner, J.; Ahlswede, E.; Docampo, P.; Bein, T.; Powalla, M. Universal Nanoparticle Wetting Agent for Upscaling Perovskite Solar Cells. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, *11* (13), 12948–12957. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b22206>.
- (82) Deng, Y.; Zheng, X.; Bai, Y.; Wang, Q.; Zhao, J.; Huang, J. Surfactant-Controlled Ink Drying Enables High-Speed Deposition of Perovskite Films for Efficient Photovoltaic Modules. *Nat. Energy* **2018**, *3* (7), 560–566. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-018-0153-9>.
- (83) Subbiah, A. S.; Isikgor, F. H.; Howells, C. T.; De Bastiani, M.; Liu, J.; Aydin, E.; Furlan, F.; Allen, T. G.; Xu, F.; Zhumagali, S.; Hoogland, S.; Sargent, E. H.; McCulloch, I.; De Wolf, S. High-Performance Perovskite Single-Junction and Textured Perovskite/Silicon

- Tandem Solar Cells via Slot-Die-Coating. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2020**, *5* (9), 3034–3040.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acseenergylett.0c01297>.
- (84) Wu, W.; Rudd, P. N.; Wang, Q.; Yang, Z.; Huang, J. Blading Phase-Pure Formamidinium-Alloyed Perovskites for High-Efficiency Solar Cells with Low Photovoltage Deficit and Improved Stability. *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, *32* (28), 2000995.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202000995>.
- (85) Küffner, J.; Wahl, T.; Hanisch, J.; Hempel, W.; Ahlswede, E.; Powalla, M. Blade Coating Perovskite Solar Cells: Impacts of Surfactant in Absorber Layer. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Hybrid and Organic Photovoltaics (HOPV19)*; 2019.
- (86) Zheng, X.; Chen, B.; Dai, J.; Fang, Y.; Bai, Y.; Lin, Y.; Wei, H.; Zeng, X. C.; Huang, J. Defect Passivation in Hybrid Perovskite Solar Cells Using Quaternary Ammonium Halide Anions and Cations. *Nat. Energy* **2017**, *2* (7), 17102.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nenergy.2017.102>.
- (87) Yang, F.; Dong, L.; Jang, D.; Saparov, B.; Tam, K. C.; Zhang, K.; Li, N.; Brabec, C. J.; Egelhaaf, H. Low Temperature Processed Fully Printed Efficient Planar Structure Carbon Electrode Perovskite Solar Cells and Modules. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2021**, 2101219.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202101219>.
- (88) Du, M.; Zhu, X.; Wang, L.; Wang, H.; Feng, J.; Jiang, X.; Cao, Y.; Sun, Y.; Duan, L.; Jiao, Y.; Wang, K.; Ren, X.; Yan, Z.; Pang, S.; Liu, S. (Frank). High-Pressure Nitrogen-Extraction and Effective Passivation to Attain Highest Large-Area Perovskite Solar Module Efficiency. *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, 2004979, 2004979.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202004979>.

- (89) Al-Ashouri, A.; Köhnen, E.; Li, B.; Magomedov, A.; Hempel, H.; Caprioglio, P.; Márquez, J. A.; Morales Vilches, A. B.; Kasparavicius, E.; Smith, J. A.; Phung, N.; Menzel, D.; Grischek, M.; Kegelmann, L.; Skroblin, D.; Gollwitzer, C.; Malinauskas, T.; Jošt, M.; Matič, G.; Rech, B.; Schlatmann, R.; Topič, M.; Korte, L.; Abate, A.; Stannowski, B.; Neher, D.; Stolterfoht, M.; Unold, T.; Getautis, V.; Albrecht, S. Monolithic Perovskite/Silicon Tandem Solar Cell with >29% Efficiency by Enhanced Hole Extraction. *Science* (80-.). **2020**, *370* (6522), 1300–1309. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abd4016>.
- (90) Fievez, M.; Singh Rana, P. J.; Koh, T. M.; Manceau, M.; Lew, J. H.; Jamaludin, N. F.; Ghosh, B.; Bruno, A.; Cros, S.; Berson, S.; Mhaisalkar, S. G.; Leong, W. L. Slot-Die Coated Methylammonium-Free Perovskite Solar Cells with 18% Efficiency. *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* **2021**, *230*, 111189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2021.111189>.
- (91) Jaysankar, M.; Qiu, W.; Bastos, J.; Tait, J. G.; Debucquoy, M.; Paetzold, U. W.; Cheyns, D.; Poortmans, J. Crystallisation Dynamics in Wide-Bandgap Perovskite Films. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2016**, *4* (27), 10524–10531. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6TA02769E>.
- (92) Ren, X.; Yang, Z.; Yang, D.; Zhang, X.; Cui, D.; Liu, Y.; Wei, Q.; Fan, H.; Liu, S. F. Modulating Crystal Grain Size and Optoelectronic Properties of Perovskite Films for Solar Cells by Reaction Temperature. *Nanoscale* **2016**, *8* (6), 3816–3822. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5NR08935B>.
- (93) Cao, X.; Zhi, L.; Jia, Y.; Li, Y.; Cui, X.; Zhao, K.; Ci, L.; Ding, K.; Wei, J. High Annealing Temperature Induced Rapid Grain Coarsening for Efficient Perovskite Solar Cells. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2018**, *524*, 483–489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2018.04.019>.

- (94) Xu, J.; Boyd, C. C.; Yu, Z. J.; Palmstrom, A. F.; Witter, D. J.; Larson, B. W.; France, R. M.; Werner, J.; Harvey, S. P.; Wolf, E. J.; Weigand, W.; Manzoor, S.; van Hest, M. F. A. M.; Berry, J. J.; Luther, J. M.; Holman, Z. C.; McGehee, M. D. Triple-Halide Wide-Band Gap Perovskites with Suppressed Phase Segregation for Efficient Tandems. *Science* (80-.). **2020**, *367* (6482), 1097–1104. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaz5074>.
- (95) Saliba, M.; Etgar, L. Current Density Mismatch in Perovskite Solar Cells. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2020**, *5* (9), 2886–2888. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenergylett.0c01642>.
- (96) Chen, B.; Yu, Z.; Liu, K.; Zheng, X.; Liu, Y.; Shi, J.; Spronk, D.; Rudd, P. N.; Holman, Z.; Huang, J. Grain Engineering for Perovskite/Silicon Monolithic Tandem Solar Cells with Efficiency of 25.4%. *Joule* **2019**, *3* (1), 177–190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2018.10.003>.

SYNOPSIS

Replacing the commonly used toxic precursor solution solvent systems by a green solvent provides a useful route for perovskite deposition by scalable printing techniques, which brings ecologically friendly solution processing of perovskite solar cells closer to application.

TOC

